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**FAMILY COMMUNICATION PATTERNS AND PRACTICE OF CHILD RIGHTS
AMONG INTERMEDIATE ELEMENTARY STUDENTS
IN A SCHOOL IN SILANG, CAVITE**

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12 August 2024

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This paper prepared by **MARY ROCELLE A. BINAORO** with the title: **“FAMILY COMMUNICATION PATTERNS AND PRACTICE OF CHILD RIGHTS AMONG INTERMEDIATE ELEMENTARY STUDENTS IN A SCHOOL IN SILANG, CAVITE”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Program.

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Biographical Sketch

The researcher, Mary Rocelle A. Binaoro started her academic journey at the University of the Philippines – Manila with a Bachelor of Arts degree in Organizational Communication. A dedicated community volunteer and a lifelong learner, her diploma has equipped her with the knowledge and necessary skills in interpersonal communication, organizational dynamics, and strategic management.

Her professional career started with focus on international client relations and support. This honed her experiences and excellence in dealing with cross-cultural clientele with diverse backgrounds refining her capacity to deliver exceptional service in a global context. To leverage her expertise in continuous learning and growth within the organization, Rocelle transitioned into the role of a Corporate Trainer within a financial and investments firm. This experience has allowed her to educate and empower employees both in their commercial marketing skills and behavioral expertise.

Presently, Rocelle embraces the role of a full-time devoted mother to two teenagers. Taking every day as a challenge to fulfill her role as a parent and at the same time fulfilling her commitment to community service. She volunteers part-time at their municipality's Women's and Child Protection Unit advocating the welfare and respect of rights to these vulnerable members of the society.

The profound dedication to personal and professional development has allowed Rocelle to journey on an intricate and elaborate path that has enhanced her resilience and adaptability into the fast-changing world. Her experiences as a student,

professional, and as a community volunteer have enriched her academic advocacy in her pursuit to complete her master's thesis.

In this study, Rocelle will examine the existing relationship between Family Communication Patterns and Child Rights Practice among Intermediate Elementary Students in a School in Silang, Cavite. Her academic background, professional experiences and personal understandings have provided relevantly to her study.

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Dedication

This thesis is dedicated to the extraordinary individuals who have illuminated my path and enriched my journey toward scholarly success.

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To my children Luis and Iya, Everything that I do, is for you. You both are my heart's greatest treasures. Seeing how you strive to achieve your dreams inspires me to do the same. I carry your dreams alongside mine fueled by the hope of a brighter future for us. May this thesis serve as a testament to boundless possibilities and may it remind you that nothing is impossible with the grace of our Lord coupled with dedication and perseverance.

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Abstract

The Sustainable Development Goals were created with the dream to uphold, and empower each member of society. These goals are linked to specific human rights that aim to achieve a transformative society by placing everyone at the center of development – leaving no one behind. The children who are the most vulnerable members of the community and future leaders of the society deserve to be protected and respected with their rights as the future lies in their hands.

This study identified the different Family Communication Patterns on the families of Intermediate Elementary Students in a School in Silang Cavite and analyzed the relationship between the different Family Communication Patterns with child rights practice. Through the research instruments used, quantitative results have revealed the prevailing Family Communication Patterns based on Conversation and Conformity orientation. Each type were ranked as Consensual being the most frequent type of Family Communication Pattern followed by Pluralistic, Protective, and Laissez-Faire. The Spearman-Rho Correlation test has shown a positive relationship between Conversation and child rights practice. Though Conformity has presented a weaker positive relationship, it still yields an increase in child rights practice as conformity level increases. This study has exposed the value of open communication in the practice of children's rights.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goals, Children's Rights, Family Communicaton

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

To deny people their human rights is to challenge their very humanity.”

Nelson Mandela

(Breakenridge, 2021).

Every person is entitled to their inherent rights, which stem from their human dignity. These encompass civil, political, economic, cultural, and social rights, ensuring comprehensive protection throughout their lives (Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2016). Upholding these rights enables individuals to shape their futures with fairness and self-respect.

Aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals, the United Nations encourages collective efforts to combat poverty and protect the environment. Developing countries have acknowledged the necessity of prioritizing progress for comprehensive development. Human rights form the foundation of the Sustainable Development Goals, as stated by the United Nations Sustainable Development Group (2023). "The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development envisions sustainable development rooted in international human rights standards, emphasizing equality and non-discrimination, and covering economic, social, civil, political, and cultural rights, as well as the right to development."

The 17 Global Goals are intricately linked to specific human rights, aiming to foster a transformative society by centering development on every individual, irrespective of race, ethnicity, religion, or cultural background, thus empowering all people to drive change. Achieving these goals highlights children's rights, focusing on inclusion and eradicating discrimination and inequalities. Sustainable Development Goals 2, 3, and 4 emphasize the importance of programs that enhance community conditions, particularly for children, and secure a sustainable future for younger generations.

Sustainable Development Goal 2 – Zero Hunger aspires to eliminate hunger by 2030. Well-nourished children are better equipped for academic success, community involvement, and resilience against illness and emergencies. Sustainable Development Goal 3 – Good Health and Well-Being aims to improve quality of life for all, from birth throughout life, addressing critical health issues like reproductive, maternal, infant, child, and adolescent health, and ensuring universal healthcare access. Sustainable Development Goal 4 – Quality Education ensures that all children receive quality education. Equal access to education supports lifelong learning, especially for vulnerable groups such as poor children, rural children, those with disabilities, indigenous people, and refugees. Quality education equips them with essential skills, enabling them to become productive adults (SDG Goal 17: Partnerships for the Goals-UNICEF Data, 2021).

Table 1: Sustainable Development Goals 2, 3 and 4 and Related Human Rights

(United Nations Human Rights, Office of the High Commissioner, N.d.)

<p>2 ZERO HUNGER</p>	<p>Right to Adequate Food</p> <p>International cooperation including ensuring equitable distribution of world food supplies</p>
<p>3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING</p>	<p>Right to Life</p> <p>Right to Health</p> <p>Special Protection to Mothers and children</p> <p>Right to enjoy the benefits of scientific progress and its applications</p> <p>International cooperation particularly in relation to the right to health and children's rights</p>
<p>4 QUALITY EDUCATION</p>	<p>Right to Education</p> <p>Equal Rights of Women and Girls in the field of education</p> <p>Right to Work including Technical and Vocational Training</p> <p>International cooperation particularly in relation to children, persons with disabilities, and indigenous peoples</p>

The Philippines is actively pursuing the Sustainable Development Goals, embracing inclusivity for all individuals regardless of ethnicity, age, gender, or ability. As part of this effort, it is crucial to prioritize the development of children, who represent the future. Upholding children's rights grants essential freedoms to those under 18, ensuring protection for future generations. Republic Act 7610 defines children as individuals under 18 or those older who are unable to protect themselves from abuse or neglect due to physical or mental conditions.

As of 2023, there are approximately 41,929,312 children in the Philippines under 18 (UNICEF). The Philippine National Baseline Study on Violence Against Children shows the country's strong commitment to implementing children's rights. However, 80 percent of Filipino children have experienced some form of violence, whether at home, school, work, or in the community (CNN Philippines, 2023). The Philippines also ranks first globally for child sexual exploitation cases (ABS-CBN News, 2022), highlighting the challenges in safeguarding children's welfare.

The home environment plays a crucial role in protecting children's rights. Parents are responsible for acting on behalf of their children, ensuring their education, development, security, health, and morality (Ba, N.d.). A child's relationship with their parents or guardians is foundational to understanding and realizing their rights. Research by Shao and Kang (2022) on Chinese participants found that the parent-child connection, learning motivation, and academic self-efficacy are vital for learning engagement.

Effective communication is essential for enhancing children's understanding of their rights. Open dialogue helps children trust and express their needs and desires, increasing their awareness and ability to exercise their rights. This communication can also empower children to protect themselves from potential threats.

Families are the primary support system for children, influencing their development and providing education on community ethics and standards. Roostin (2018) demonstrated the family's role as the first educational environment, emphasizing its impact on a child's understanding of societal norms. Family communication significantly affects behavior, as evidenced by Iftikhar and Raza's (2017) study on Pakistani girls, which found a positive correlation between family communication and leadership behavior. Abdullah and Mini (2020) also found that family communication patterns can mitigate behavioral issues in children, linking parenting style to empathy.

While existing literature underscores the importance of family communication in child development, the connection between family communication patterns and the practice of children's rights remains underexplored. This study aims to investigate the role of current family communication patterns in the practice of children's rights within selected Filipino households. By understanding these patterns, the study seeks to elucidate their relevance to the practice of children's rights.

Statement of the Problem

The general problem is:

How Family Communication Patterns Correlate with Child Rights Practice

The specific research questions are:

1. What are the different family communication patterns that exist within Filipino families?
2. What is the relationship between family communication patterns and child rights practice among children?

Objectives of the Study

In general, the study aims to determine the relationship between family communication patterns to child rights practice.

The following are the specific objectives of the study:

1. Determine the different family communication patterns in families of Intermediate Elementary Students
2. Explain the relationship between the different family communication patterns and child rights practices among children.

Significance of the Study

Children are among the most vulnerable populations worldwide, revealing a significant gap in the realization of their rights. This vulnerability hinders their growth and ability to thrive, despite national progress. To address this issue, it is crucial for society to strengthen efforts to uphold children's rights, starting with the family. Regardless of structure, every family has the responsibility to ensure that a child's basic needs are met, as the home environment is vital for their survival, safety, and development, serving as the foundation for their upbringing.

Dolan et al. (2019) highlight the importance of the family in safeguarding children's rights, as emphasized by the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC). The preamble of the UNCRC identifies the family as "the fundamental group of society and the natural environment for the growth and well-being of all its members, particularly children," and stresses the need for families to be supported in fulfilling their responsibilities (Office of the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights, 1994). A child's civil rights, including birth registration, naming, and nationality, begin within the family, forming the basis of their identity. As children mature, the family's role in fostering awareness of children's rights becomes crucial, with family values shaping respect for oneself and others. Families are central to the recognition and practice of children's rights, providing essential support for their well-being and development.

This research aims to deepen our understanding of how family communication influences the fulfillment of children's rights. By examining the role of the family—the fundamental unit of society—in promoting children's well-being, we can better support

their growth and advancement. Communities can collaborate with families to create a society that is non-discriminatory, equitable, and protective of children's rights, ensuring every child's basic freedoms are safeguarded. The voices of children must be heard, and raising awareness and acceptance of children's rights can help cultivate a culture of peace, pluralism, and inclusion in society.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This research aims to explore various family communication patterns and their association with the implementation of children's rights. It will concentrate on Filipino families with Intermediate Elementary Students in Silang, Cavite, irrespective of their family structure (extended, nuclear, single-parent, or guardianship). The study will specifically address Sustainable Development Goals 2 (Zero Hunger), 3 (Good Health and Well-Being), and 4 (Quality Education). It will not investigate children's or parents' awareness of rights but will focus solely on how family communication influences the practice of these rights.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

. Review of Related Literature

Children have the right to flourish, reach their full potential, and live in an environment that supports sustainability. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development emphasizes the need to prioritize children's rights and develop inclusive strategies to achieve these objectives.

The linkage between human rights and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is crucial for progress and sustainability. Effective development policies improve human protection, and upholding human rights is integral to advancing the 2030 Agenda. A June 2017 conference at the Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development in Bonn, Germany, underscored this connection, illustrating that the 2030 Agenda's success hinges on the protection of human rights.

One primary goal of the SDGs is poverty reduction. Despite substantial efforts, poverty remains a pressing challenge, with many communities unable to fulfill their basic needs. The United Nations Development Programme reports that 736 million people live in extreme poverty, half of whom are children, and one in ten people endure severe poverty. Utilizing evidence-based human rights approaches, both qualitative and quantitative, is essential for fostering collective action and social engagement to

achieve the SDG goal of eradicating poverty (Sano, 2020). The inclusion of health and social security in the 2030 Agenda highlights the importance of social protection and universal healthcare (Kaltenborn, 2020), emphasizing the need to meet the SDG related to Good Health and Well-Being.

Gender equality is another critical aspect of Agenda 2030. Achieving this involves eliminating violence, ensuring equal resource access, fostering equitable participation, and empowering women. Implementing transformative measures to advance women's rights and protect against gender-based violence is vital for reducing exclusion and discrimination, thereby making the SDGs more attainable (Rudolf, 2020).

The right to peace, justice, and strong institutions enhances individual empowerment and improves governance, which supports community development (Lazarus, 2020). Environmental sustainability also significantly impacts human well-being. Ensuring environmental protection and sustainability is essential for a safe and healthy future. Collaborative efforts among stakeholders are needed to align human rights with environmental and climate objectives (Boyle, 2020).

Children's Rights. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) provide a strategic framework to equip the younger generation with the essential knowledge, skills, services, and support they need to become active and valued members of society. Ensuring respect for children's rights is crucial to securing their survival and maximizing their potential as future contributors to society. A report by the Office of

the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (2016) underscores the urgency of prioritizing children's rights, highlighting alarming statistics such as:

- Nearly 570 million children living in extreme poverty
- 230 million children under age five not officially registered at birth
- One billion children facing physical, sexual, and psychological abuse
- One in five girls experiencing sexual abuse at least once in their lives
- 119,000 children under age five dying from preventable causes like unsafe drinking water
- 250 million children lacking basic literacy due to poor education quality

Realizing children's rights is essential for granting fundamental freedoms to every individual under 18.

These rights acknowledge that children are not merely extensions of their parents but are individuals with their own identities and entitlements. The UN General Assembly ratified the Convention on the Rights of the Child, outlining rights that support children in becoming valued members of society. UNICEF emphasizes the importance of human dignity for all children and advocates for the universal application of children's rights. The Convention on the Rights of the Child stresses that children should be heard and considered as individuals, with their well-being directly impacting societal health. Respecting children's rights is crucial for protecting future generations of leaders and citizens. The Convention safeguards children's civil, political, economic, social, health, and cultural rights, affirming that all these rights are equally important. Understanding and practicing child rights fosters scholarly discussions about children's needs, which are often best expressed through their rights.

Research by Steinberg (2016) indicates that children's brains develop rapidly at a young age, enhancing their emotional control, executive skills, and social connections. Prioritizing the exercise of their rights within families is essential for this development, leading to better social relationships and a clearer sense of self as they grow into adolescence. UNICEF (2019) aims to promote the global recognition and practice of child rights. The organization advocates for upholding fundamental principles of child development through the practice of these rights within all family structures. Achieving this involves a balanced approach between dialogue and conformity, creating an environment where children's rights are respected and empowered. This not only benefits children's development and well-being but also prepares them to be responsible and valuable members of society. Prioritizing and taking transformative action on children's rights will drive sustainable development, breaking the cycle of current societal issues and enabling multiple developmental gains, leading to accelerated progress.

Children's Rights in the Philippines. The Philippines actively supports and upholds children's rights, with the government responsible for implementing measures to ensure these rights are realized. This includes providing access to essential services, preventing abuse and exploitation, and supporting children in reaching their full potential. Despite these efforts, data from the Philippine National Baseline Study on Violence Against Children, highlighted by World Vision, reveal significant challenges in protecting Filipino children:

- Approximately 20% of children are sexually abused, whether at home, in school, or within their community.
- Around 40% experience bullying from their peers.

- Nearly 60% suffer from psychological abuse.
- A staggering 80% are exposed to physical violence within their households.
- Half of all children fall victim to cyber violence.
- About 60% endure both physical and psychological abuse.
- 70% of children lack access to local protective services in their communities.

Every child is entitled to the rights of life, growth, and protection, yet violence and exploitation pose significant threats to their development. Harracksingh and Janagan (2022) explored the effects of sexual assault on children in Trinidad and Tobago, revealing that such trauma often results in post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), poor academic outcomes, feelings of isolation, depression, and deep emotional scars. In another study, Nelson and Quiton (2018) examined child labor in the Philippines, highlighting its adverse impacts on children's education, health, and leisure. Their findings suggest that reducing work hours and burdens can lower school dropout rates, whereas intensive physical labor detrimentally affects educational attainment. Children working in agriculture faced exposure to parasites and harmful germs, while those in industrial settings dealt with extreme temperatures and toxic chemicals, leaving them with little opportunity for recreation.

Bullying also inflicts significant harm on children's physical, educational, and emotional well-being, leading to increased absenteeism, declining academic performance, and various health problems. Even those who witness bullying can suffer, showing a higher likelihood of substance use and experiencing depression and

anxiety. De Veyra (2019) discussed the long-term impacts of physical and psychological abuse, which include challenges in forming meaningful relationships and emotional detachment. Over time, the cumulative effects of abuse and violence can be devastating. De Veyra's research (2019) further noted that the infringement of children's rights is widespread in households, schools, and communities. Addressing these issues requires a holistic strategy involving the government, stakeholders, communities, and families. The Philippines has been a strong advocate for child protection, with Angelo M. Tapales, Executive Director of the Council for the Welfare of Children, emphasizing the need for intensified efforts to uphold children's rights.

Family in the Philippines. In the Philippines, the family is a deeply respected institution, as enshrined in Article 2, Section 12 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution. This provision recognizes the sanctity of the family and mandates state protection for both the mother and the unborn child from conception. It also highlights the primary role of parents in raising children with a sense of civic duty and moral integrity, supported by government initiatives. Article XV, Section 1, further identifies the Filipino family as the cornerstone of the nation, with Section 3, number 2, stressing the state's responsibility to safeguard children's rights to adequate care, nutrition, and protection from neglect, abuse, and exploitation (Official Gazette, n.d.).

Filipino families are instrumental in nurturing children's development, typically structured as single-parent households, nuclear families, or extended families (National Statistics Office, 2009). The family's influence is vital for promoting harmony and societal progress, with parents serving as key role models who instill responsibility and productivity (Yangco, n.d.). However, as children mature, the family's influence

may diminish, though parental oversight remains crucial in mitigating external influences such as media and peers (Cruz et al., 2001). Family involvement is critical to various aspects of child development, including welfare, education, and behavioral health ("Benefits of Family Engagement," 2018). Effective communication within the family fosters understanding, problem-solving, unity, and trust, allowing parents to impart essential values and lessons that guide children to become fair and responsible members of society (Runcan et al., 2012).

Communication is a crucial element of a comprehensive strategy to promote the health and well-being of children and adolescents, protect the vulnerable, and support those facing significant challenges (Ramirez, 2022; UNICEF, 2021). Research has highlighted the importance of family communication patterns in children's development. For instance, Ramlan and Suyurno (2019) found that family communication is key to creating a healthy home environment and positively influences juvenile personality development. Simon (2021) noted that parenting inherently involves communication, as it is the means by which parents teach norms and values.

Hurst et al. (2021) emphasized the importance of parent-child communication in adolescent sexual decision-making, highlighting its positive impact on sexual self-efficacy, intentions to discuss sex with partners, and condom use. The frequency and quality of parent-child communication significantly influence teenagers' sexual behavior, demonstrating the broader relevance of family communication in various developmental areas.

Family Communication Patterns. The way families interact and establish norms shapes their communication patterns. The diverse viewpoints and values within a family influence how information flows between members. Littlejohn and Foss (2009) outlined four family communication patterns defined by Koerner and Fitzpatrick (2002):

1. **Consensual:** Characterized by high levels of both discussion and uniformity. Parents listen to their children but encourage them to adopt the family's beliefs.
2. **Pluralistic:** Values conversation over conformity. Open communication is prevalent, and parents do not seek to control their children's views.
3. **Protective:** Prioritizes uniformity over communication. Parents control the conversation, making decisions for their children who rely on established rules.
4. **Laissez-faire:** Involves minimal engagement among family members, with low levels of both conformity and conversation. Children make decisions independently without much parental guidance.

These patterns are heavily influenced by the family's communication style, which can either be oriented towards conversation or conformity. Conversation orientation promotes open and ongoing exchanges of ideas, thoughts, and emotions among family members. In contrast, conformity orientation is more authoritarian and less concerned with children's thoughts and feelings.

Balancing these two elements is crucial, as evidenced by various studies. Hessen and Dworkin (2018) found that consensual communication, which balances

conversation and conformity, foster respect for family norms and children's rights. Tenenbaum et al. (2021) noted that emphasizing conformity helps children understand responsibility and mutual respect. Buehler, Franck, and Cook (2020) highlighted that focusing on conversation enhances children's ability to voice their opinions and advocate for their rights. Conversely, Eden and Schrodtt (2019) warned that neglecting both conversation and conformity can lead to children feeling unsupported and neglected, hindering their ability to advocate for their rights.

Analyzing these patterns reveals that family communication significantly influences a child's development and their ability to practice their rights. According to Koerner and Schrodtt (2018), effective communication fosters open and supportive relationships within families, aiding children's social and emotional development. An environment where children feel understood and valued is essential for their psychological well-being. Conformity within families provides a sense of security, ensuring that children's independence and unique identities are respected (Newman & Harrison, 2018). A balanced approach that combines conversation and conformity offers a supportive framework for understanding and practicing children's rights (Lansdown, 2019).

Theoretical Construct

The Family Communication Patterns Theory informs this study by highlighting the role of family communication in constructing a shared social reality. Research on this topic has examined various intrapersonal and interpersonal dynamics, showing that family communication impacts both individual cognition and behavior, as well as the family system as a whole. Families create a common social reality through two main behavioral aspects.

Figure 1. Family Communication Types (Koerner & Fitzpatrick, 2006).

1. Conversation Orientation: This refers to the frequency and openness of communication among family members. In families with high conversation orientation, members frequently discuss family activities, decisions, and personal matters,

fostering friendly and supportive relationships. Conversely, families with low conversation orientation communicate less often and share fewer intimate thoughts and feelings.

2. Conformity Orientation: This aspect measures the extent to which family members share similar attitudes, values, and beliefs. In high conformity families, children and younger members are expected to obey their parents and elders, resulting in a unified and hierarchical structure where parents make decisions for the family. In contrast, low-conformity families value individualism and personal space, with members holding diverse attitudes and beliefs.

These two orientations often interact, influencing family outcomes. Koerner and Fitzpatrick (2006) identified four family types based on the interaction of conversation and conformity orientations:

- 1. Consensual Families:** These families exhibit high levels of both communication and conformity. They prioritize maintaining family structure while encouraging open communication. However, parents ultimately make decisions, expecting children to adopt their belief system.
- 2. Pluralistic Families:** With high conversation and low conformity, these families engage in open, unrestricted discussions involving all members. Parents are open to their children's viewpoints and allow them to participate in decision-making processes.
- 3. Protective Families:** Characterized by low conversation and high conformity, these families emphasize obedience to parental authority with minimal open communication. Parents make decisions without

explaining them to children, and conflicts are viewed negatively, resulting in limited family engagement.

4. Laissez-Faire Families: These families have low levels of both conversation and conformity. Interactions are minimal, with parents showing little interest in their children's decisions and being emotionally detached. Children receive minimal support and guidance from their parents.

Understanding these family communication patterns provides insight into how family interactions shape individual development and behavior. The balance of conversation and conformity orientations can significantly influence family dynamics and outcomes.

Conceptual Framework

This model effectively illustrates the connection between Family Communication Patterns and children's awareness of their rights. As previously mentioned, a child's family profoundly influences their knowledge, behavior, and overall development. This study will use this conceptual model to either support or challenge the Family Communication Patterns Theory. According to Koerner and Fitzpatrick (2006), the theory posits that behaviors impact family functioning not because they are inherently functional or dysfunctional, but due to how they operate within the specific communication contexts established by different family types.

The involved variables in the study are family communication patterns acting as the independent, while the child rights practice for the dependent variable. Family communication pattern is the extent to which all family members, especially children, are included in discussions and can participate meaningfully in decision-making processes. On the other hand, child rights practice is the act of equipping the essential needs for children's physical, mental, educational, and emotional development. It also includes the ability and freedom of children to express their opinions, thoughts, and feelings within the family, and to participate in family decisions, especially those affecting them.

Family communication patterns are measured through two orientation factors such as conversation and conformity. Conversation deals with differentiation between socio-oriented communication, which prioritizes harmony and avoidance of conflict, and concept-oriented communication, which encourages exploring and debating

ideas. While, conformity is the degree to which family communication encourages open discussion, sharing of feelings and ideas, and individual expression versus conformity to family norms and decisions without question. Moreover, by determining the levels of these two as low or high, specific family communication pattern of the child will be determined into Consensual, Pluralistic, Protective, and Laissez-Faire. After exploring the family communication patterns of the children, its relationship to the practice of their rights was analyzed. In this way, the hypotheses of the study were answered, if belonging to any of the types such as Consensual, Pluralistic, Protective, and Laissez-Faire will lead to a high level of child rights practice.

Figure 2

Family Communication Pattern Theory of Koerner and Fitzpatrick as Applied to the Child Rights Practice Among Public Intermediate Students of School A in Silang, Cavite

A Conceptual Paradigm

Adapted From: Koerner, A. F., & Fitzpatrick, M. A., 2006.

Operational Definition of Terms

1. Communication - the communicative connection in the family that enhances the children's understanding and exercise of their rights. This can be assessed through children's knowledge of their rights, their perceived ability to exercise these rights, and observable instances of rights being exercised within the family context.

2. Family Communication Pattern - the extent to which all family members, especially children, are included in discussions affecting their rights and can participate meaningfully in decision-making processes.

3. Conversation Orientation - Differentiating between socio-oriented communication, which prioritizes harmony and avoidance of conflict, and concept-oriented communication, which encourages exploring and debating ideas.

4. Conformity Orientation - the degree to which family communication encourages open discussion, sharing of feelings and ideas, and individual expression versus conformity to family norms and decisions without question.

5. Children's Rights - the provision of healthcare, nutritious food, clean water, adequate living conditions, and quality education. And, the extent to which children are allowed to express their views on matters affecting them and the extent to which these views are considered in family decisions.

6. Children's Rights Practice - the act of equipping the essential needs for children's physical, mental, educational, and emotional development. It also includes the ability and freedom of children to express their opinions, thoughts, and feelings within the family, and to participate in family decisions, especially those affecting them.

Hypotheses of the Study

This study is guided by a series of hypotheses that will lead the researcher's inquiry and will provide a structured framework for the study's investigation.

H1: A consensual type of family communication leads to a high level of practice of a child's rights.

H2: A pluralistic type of family communication leads to a high level of practice of child's rights.

H3: A protective type of family communication leads to a high level of practice of child's rights.

H4: A Laissez-faire type of family communication leads to a high level of practice of child's rights.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research will utilize a quantitative approach through a cross-sectional survey to collect data. It will employ both descriptive and analytical techniques to present and interpret the findings. The analysis aims to reveal how various family communication patterns impact children's well-being and assess whether there is a correlation between these communication styles and the practice of children's rights.

Locale of the Study

The research took place at Silang West Elementary School, situated in Silang Cavite, specifically in Silang Poblacion, Barangay 5. This institution is part of the Silang Central School system, with facilities spread across residential areas and nearby communities, including San Vicente and Barangay Tubuan. Covering an area of 10,000 square meters, the school complex comprises 10 buildings and 21 classrooms.

With a history spanning fifty years, Silang West Elementary School has consistently embraced changes and advancements in the educational system. Currently, the school offers a curriculum for Grades V and VI that adheres to the Basic

Education Curriculum (BEC), focusing on core subjects such as English, Mathematics, Science, Health, Filipino, and MAKABAYAN (including SK/Sibika, MSEP, EPP, and

Respondents of the Study

This study targets Intermediate Elementary Students (Grade Six) aged 11-14 from public schools in Metro Silang, Cavite. The selection of this age group is intentional, as these students possess the cognitive abilities to comprehend, analyze, and respond to survey and interview questions effectively, despite their young age. The World Health Organization (2022) highlights that individuals in this age bracket are particularly vulnerable to various forms of abuse and violence, whether from family members, caregivers, peers, or strangers.

The study will focus on sixth-grade students from a public school in Metro Silang, specifically targeting approximately 4 to 5 sections, each with 30 to 40 students. To ensure comprehensive representation, every section will be included in the study. The selected students will complete survey questionnaires designed to identify the family communication patterns they experience and assess how their rights as children are conveyed and upheld within their families.

Sampling Scheme

The study shall employ stratified random sampling in gathering respondents. Considering a minimum number of 4 sections for Grade Six students, with a total of

25 students per class, a complete list of names will be gathered and numbered each name accordingly. The total sample size needed will be divided equally among the 4 sections and random sampling will be employed. Using Slovin's formula, the sample size needed is 80. With that, 20 students each will be gathered as respondents. The researcher decided to exhibit randomization by getting the even-numbered students in the master lists of each class. However, due to the availability of almost all of the entire population of the Grade six students, the researcher was able to gather up to 132 respondents.

Research Instruments

The primary method for gathering data in this study will be a survey questionnaire, structured in two parts. The first part will evaluate the communication patterns within the participants' families, using an adapted version of Richie and Fitzpatrick's (2002) Family Communication Patterns Questionnaire, including extra subcategories to assess Conversation and Conformity levels. Responses will be recorded using a 5-point Likert scale, from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

The second part, designed by the researcher, will explore how children's rights are addressed and practiced within the family, in alignment with the World Health Organization's Sustainable Development Goals such as Zero Hunger, Good Health and Well-Being, and Quality Education. This section will also use a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

. Data Gathering Procedure

The study will primarily use a survey questionnaire to gather data. This tool is structured into two distinct sections: one focusing on family communication patterns and the other on the implementation of children's rights within the family. This structure is essential for exploring how these two elements interact.

The initial section will adapt Richie and Fitzpatrick's (2002) Family Communication Patterns Questionnaire, adding subcategories to measure the levels of Conversation and Conformity. Responses will be recorded using a 5-point Likert scale, from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Prior to data collection, the researcher will seek approval from a Research Panel to address any concerns regarding the sensitive nature of the study and the involvement of minors. Additionally, approval will be obtained from the principal of the participating Elementary Public School to facilitate the research and ensure reliable data collection (refer to Appendix B). The survey will be administered under the supervision of the class adviser and school guidance counselor. Parental consent will be obtained beforehand to protect participant anonymity and secure permission for their children's involvement in the study.

Ethical Considerations

Treatment of the Study – Data collected will be treated with utmost privacy and confidentiality. All the information collected will only be used for the purpose of this study. For this research involving minors, data were collected through structured surveys administered in a classroom setting under the supervision of class advisers and school guidance counselor. Before data collection, written consent forms were distributed to parents or legal guardians, explaining the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and their rights regarding their child's participation. Only those minors whose parents or legal guardians provided informed consent were allowed to participate. No data collected from the study, including individual responses or identifiable information, will be shared with any third parties.

Benefits of Participants - Respondents should participate based on informed consent. Approval from the School Principal will be sought and letters will be distributed to the sample population's parents/guardians. The privacy and anonymity of respondents will be considered. The insights provided by minors through their participation contribute to the advancement of knowledge and understanding in the field of Communication. By actively involving minors in the research process, this study aims to generate findings that are more representative and reflective of the diverse experiences and viewpoints within the target population. By participating in this study, minors are able to share their experiences and viewpoints on impotent issues such as realization of children's rights that can contribute to the development of policies, programs and interventions that address societal challenges and improve the well-being of individuals and communities.

Expert Review – To ensure the reliability, validity, and ethical soundness of the research instruments, an expert review with a Psychometrician was sought. This review process aimed to assess the suitability of the study design, measures, and procedures, particularly to the involvement of minors and the sensitive nature of the research topic. Furthermore, the School Guidance Counselor also validated the clarity, comprehensibility and appropriateness of the survey items making sure that the instruments were age-appropriate and comprehensible for minors. Any concerns raised by the experts regarding the ethical implications of the research were carefully considered and addressed to mitigate potential risks and ensure the welfare of the participants.

Inclusion Criteria – Careful consideration of ethical principles and sensitivity of the research topic were part of the inclusion criteria for participants in this study. Participants were minors aged 10-14 capable of providing meaningful insights into family communication and their experiences in child rights practice. Participants provided informed consent on their participation in the research with their parental or legal guardian's consent. Participants were fluent in English to ensure their comprehension on the research instrument. The study was conducted on a defined Educational Institution to confirm the accessibility and guarantee participation from identified respondents.

Data Analysis

The analysis will be done in two approaches such as descriptive and inferential statistics. In determining the existing family communication pattern per respondent, computation of weighted means will be used. A weighted mean or simply averaging will be employed to compute the levels of conversation and conformity wherein averaged scores of 3.01 - 5.00 are equivalent to high and 1.00 - 3.00 will get the description level of low. This shall be implemented for statements under conversation and conformity. High conversation and high conformity are equivalent to consensual type. High conversation but low conformity falls under the pluralistic type. Low conversation and high conformity are in the protective type. And lastly, low conversation and low conformity are sides of the Laissez-Faire type. This computation is directly imposed in Richie and Fitzpatrick's model for family communication pattern questionnaires as well.

In the second research question, measuring the significant relationship between the types of family communication patterns and the practice of children's rights, the median shall be computed. After the determination of the family communication pattern of the respondents, they will be grouped according to their family type where the median levels of the scores of the respondents in terms of the practice of their rights shall be computed. The median scores shall indicate the level of child rights practice per family type.

Lastly, in measuring the significant relationship between the observed variables, inferential statistics will be employed using a correlation test. This is to directly analyze the hypothesis of the study which is belonging to a specific type of family communication pattern from Consensual, Pluralistic, Protective and Laissez-faire do not lead to high level of child rights practice. The Spearman Rho Correlation is suitable for analyzing data obtained from survey questionnaires that utilize a 5-point Likert scale. This statistical tool will be used to determine if there is a significant relationship between ranked types of numerical data like the Likert scaling. The formula for Spearman Rho correlation at 95% level of significance and interpretation are as follows:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{N \sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{[N \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][N \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Where:

N=number of respondents x=first variable y=second variable

Correlation coefficient	Interpretation
r=0.0	No correlation
0.0<r<0.2	Very weak correlation
0.2<r<0.4	Weak Correlation
0.4<r<0.6	Moderate Correlation
0.6<r<0.8	High correlation
r>0.8	Very high correlation

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

. This chapter presents an analysis and interpretation of survey data, addressing the research questions posed. It examines the relationship between family communication patterns and the implementation of children's rights, exploring the factors that influence children's experiences within their family settings. The discussion emphasizes the importance of communication dynamics in safeguarding and practicing children's rights.

The study is based on Koerner and Fitzpatrick's Family Communication Theory (2006), which identifies two main dimensions—Conversation and Conformity—that combine to create four distinct types of family communication: Consensual, Pluralistic, Protective, and Laissez-Faire. Conversation Orientation is characterized by the extent of open and extensive discussions within families, while Conformity Orientation relates to the level of shared attitudes, values, and beliefs fostered by family communication. Understanding these dimensions is crucial for analyzing how different communication patterns influence the practice of children's rights.

By identifying each respondent's Family Communication Pattern and its relation to the practice of child rights, this research highlights the critical role of family communication in achieving and supporting children's rights. The survey results provide insights into how family communication dynamics impact the realization of these rights.

Respondents' Profile

From four (4) sections of Grade Six Intermediate class of Silang West Elementary School, with a total number of one hundred fifty-seven (157) students, 80 is the target sample size to accomplish the survey questionnaires using Slovin's formula. During the meeting with the School Principal and School Guidance Counselor last February 7, it was suggested that the entire Intermediate population may respond to the survey questionnaires. One hundred fifty-seven (157) consent letters to parents were handed out last February 6, to which twenty-five (25) students did not attend classes on February 21 - the day the survey was completed, giving a total of one hundred thirty-two (132) survey respondents. Due to one respondent having incomplete responses, the final sample is one hundred thirty-one (131) survey respondents. Table 2 presents the characteristics of the survey questionnaire respondents where age and gender are indicated. To maintain animosity, writing their names on the respondent's profile was optional.

Table 2: Survey Questionnaire Respondents' Profile Based on Sex and Age

Respondents' Characteristics	N
Gender	
Male	72
Female	60
Age	
11	52
12	71
13	06
14	03

The study focuses on Grade Six Intermediate Elementary Students from a school in Silang, Cavite. It identifies and examines four distinct Family Communication Patterns prevalent in the respondents' families. These patterns reveal how communication is practiced within these families. The literature underscores the family's role as a fundamental institution in supporting and advancing children's rights, emphasizing its benefits in various developmental areas such as Child Welfare, Juvenile Justice, Behavioral Health, Education, and Early Childhood Education ("Benefits of Family Engagement", 2018). The study aims to explore the connection between family communication patterns and the implementation of child rights among the respondents. The goal is to uncover factors that could contribute to the

development of policies and interventions designed to promote healthier family environments, thereby enhancing the protection and well-being of Filipino children.

In terms of the demographic profiling, majority of the respondents are 12-year-olds (53.79%), predominantly male (54.55%), and a relatively balanced representation from all of the sections. Given these backgrounds, the findings of the study suggest that they primarily reflect the perspectives and experiences of the target population, which is from the early adolescence. And this stage depicts the need for critical insights of creating a conducive environment for children as this is considered as the crucial developmental stage for cognitive, social and emotional changes. This can be clearly observed in the study of Steinberg (2016), wherein he stated that early adolescence involves the process of rapid brain development; hence, the requirement for factors of improved functions, social interactions emotional regulations to be well taken handled and studied.

The strength of its foundation can be observed in the adolescence stage, wherein adults are required already to act and communicate in more advanced reasoning abilities and adept with understanding of complex ideas, relationships and situations in their lives. Furthermore, based on the same author, if children are in good family communication set-ups, this can navigate them to form stronger peer relationships that will later on help them on defining their own senses of self-being. Conceptualizing all of these, the target population of the proponent indeed shall help on the creation of developmental framework for the families, researchers and communities in enhancing the Filipino society's insights towards handling and

experiencing family environments, to exercise further the ongoing demands for the child rights practice.

Results

Research Question 1:

What are the different family communication patterns that exist within Filipino families of Intermediate Elementary Students in a School in Silang Cavite?

In identifying the existing family communication pattern per respondent, the need to determine the Level of Conversation and Level of Conformity must be established. The research instrument used was adapted from Koerner and Fitzpatrick (2002) and has used 5-point Likert scaling system where 1 means Strongly Disagree, 2 Disagree, 3 Neutral, 4 Agree, and 5 Strongly Agree. Identification of the Family Communication Pattern was based on each respondent's answer on the level of Conversation and Conformity. An individual tabulation of results can be seen in Appendix D. Summary of the results on the Level of Conversation and Conformity are in Tables 3 and 4 respectively.

Table 3: Frequency and Percentage of Respondents in Terms of Level of Conversation

Level	Frequency	Percent
High	90	68.70
Low	41	31.30
Total	131	100.00

Table 4: Frequency and Percentage of Respondents in Terms of Level of Conformity

Level	Frequency	Percent
High	100	76.34
Low	31	23.66
Total	131	100.00

Based on the results of identifying the level of Conversation and Conformity, the existing type of family communication pattern was established individually and is reflected in Appendix E. Table 5 illustrates the frequency of each family communication type from all the 131 survey respondents. With regards to the determination of the existing family communication patterns among the respondents, it is revealed that significant portion of respondents experience high levels of

conversation (68.70%) and conformity (76.34%). This signifies that indeed, more children experience both high levels of conversation and conformity. Based with Koerner and Schrodts (2018), this is a good indicator in practicing child rights as the two elements involved empower family environments. High level of conversation fosters a more supportive familial connection wherein children are encouraged to express their feelings and thoughts openly without any fear and judgement, contributing mainly to their general well-being.

On the other hand, high level of conformity strengthens further the roles of parents and other involved guardians to implicate the established norms and values that shall help in the development of children. This is the element which balances the presence of high level of conversation wherein children can be expressive while under this, the emergence of a collective family orientation allows them to feel a sense of security and stability as dependents.

For Newman and Harrison (2018), understanding the levels of conversation and conformity in family relationships is significant, specifically for Asian families as the power relations between the elders and children are evident. Especially those Filipino families are practicing strong components of societal norms and values. It is valuable as well to analyze the presence of the element of conversation, given that it is proposed in helping the children to develop their own senses as well while being purely dependent with the guidance of the elders. Given that it was imposed from the findings that respondents in the study experience both high levels of conversation and conformity, this can be expected with various positive outcomes as well. Respondents may experience better psychological health, improved problem-solving skills and

higher self-esteem, which later on be revealed in exploring the relationships of family communication patterns with child rights practice.

Table 5: Frequency and Percentage of Respondents in Terms of Type of Family Communication Pattern

Types	Frequency	Percent
Consensual	75	57.25
Protective	25	19.08
Laissez-Faire	16	12.21
Pluralistic	15	11.45
Total	131	100.00

In examining the types of family communication patterns, the majority are classified as consensual (57.25%). Consensual families are characterized by high levels of both conversation and conformity, suggesting that these families emphasize open communication while expecting adherence to family norms. Next to it are respondents with pluralistic (19.08%) type of family communication, embodying high level of conversation but low level of conformity. This set-up reflects that children are with open communication and not much adhering to the family norms. This is followed by protective (12.21%) family communication pattern, composed of those with low

level of conversation and high level of conformity wherein the communication in their families are limited and highly practicing the familial norms. Lastly, are the least represented in the study, those with laissez-faire (11.45%) type with both low levels of conversation and conformity, wherein there is lesser occurrence of open communication and low experienced adherence to the family norms.

Despite the variation among the occurrence of the four family communication patterns among the sample, the proximity of both high levels of conversation and conformity can be observed as the majority experiences of the respondents. In connection to their child rights practice, it was indicated that high level of conversation correlate with higher child rights practice ($r = 0.44, p < 0.001$). On the other hand, this relationship is synonymous with level of conformity, although weaker ($r = 0.23, p = 0.0069$). These findings suggests that experiencing both high levels of these two elements indeed resulted to high levels of child rights practice as well. This is a significant outcome for the study for it proposes that despite usual Filipino family set-up having a structured environment through the presence of strict adherence to specific norms and values as the high level of conformity reflects; still the rights of children are not being neglected. And this may achieved through the balancing act that high level of conversation creates, wherein open communication allows for the formation of independence of children as well while adhering to the familial rules.

Research Question 2:

What is the relationship between family communication patterns and child rights practice among children?

The gathered data from each respondent was able to determine the existing family communication pattern and expose how child rights are practiced for each individual. As each respondent revealed the level of conversation and conformity, an interpretation of whether High or Low practice of child rights was also illustrated.

Each Sustainable Development Goal: Goal 2- Zero Hunger, Goal 3 – Good Health and Well-Being, and Goal 4- Quality Education are represented by survey questions in Part 2 of the research questionnaire. Respondents have exposed the practice of child rights in their respective families, a detailed tabulation of results can be seen at Appendix F, G and H respectively.

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics on the Level of Child's Right Practice in Different Family Communication Patterns

	Practice			
	Consensual	Laissez-Faire	Pluralistic	Protective
Valid	75	16	15	25
Median	4.27	3.73	4.00	3.87
Minimum	3.00	2.07	2.87	2.07
Maximum	5.00	4.60	5.00	5.00

Legend: 1.00– 3.00 Low 3.01 – 5.00 High

Table 6 positions the descriptive statistics for the level of child's rights practice when the respondents are already grouped to their corresponding family communication patterns. Those respondents under the consensual type of family communication pattern have a median level of child's rights practice of 4.27 with an interpretation of high. This shows that consensual children are experiencing their rights practices in a high manner. Those who are under the laissez-faire type of family communication pattern have a median level of child's rights practice of 3.73 with an interpretation of high. This presents that children who are under the laissez-faire type are experiencing their rights practices in a high manner as well. This goes the same with those who are under the pluralistic type of family communication pattern with a median level of 4.00 and an interpretation of high. Lastly, those under the protective type of family communication pattern have a median of 3.87 with an interpretation of high. This signifies also that children under this type are experiencing a high level of child's rights practice. As observed all types of family communication patterns are exhibiting a high level of child's rights practice. Consequently, to compare the four types, consensual type has the highest median, this is followed by pluralistic, next is the protective and the last one is the laissez-faire.

Correlational Results

Table 7: Spearman Rho Correlational Testing between Levels of Conversation and Practice of Children's Rights

Variables	Rhop-value	Interpretation	Decision
Conversation - Practice	0.44 < 0.001	Moderate Positive	Significant

Table 9 depicts the spearman rho correlational testing results in order to determine the significant relationship between level of conversation of the respondents and their rights' practice. As shown, there is a moderate positive relationship between the said variables ($r = 0.44$). This signifies that as the level of conversation of the respondents increases, their level of rights' practice is also increasing and in a moderate manner. This result is statistically significant at 95% confidence level ($p < 0.001$)

Figure 3: Scatter Plot of Correlation between Levels of Conversation And Practice of Children's Rights

Figure 3 serves as the visual representation of the relationship between the levels of conversation and the rights' practice of the respondents. As shown, as the level of conversation increases, the level of rights' practice also increases, and in a moderate manner.

Table 8: Spearman Rho Correlational Testing between Levels of Conformity and Practice of Children's Rights

Variables	Rho	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Conformity - Practice	0.23	0.0069	Weak Positive	Significant

Table 8 demonstrates the Spearman rho correlational testing results in order to determine the significant relationship between level of conformity of the respondents and their rights' practice. As presented, there is a weak positive relationship between the said variables ($r = 0.23$). This signifies that as the level of conformity of the respondents increases, their level of rights' practice is also increasing and in a weak manner. This result is statistically significant at 95% confidence level ($p = 0.0069$).

Figure 4: Scatter Plot of Correlation between Levels of Conformity And Practice of Children's Rights

Figure 4 serves as the visual representation of the relationship between the levels of conformity and the child rights practice of the respondents. As presented, as the level of conformity increases, the level of child rights practice also increases, in a weak manner.

Table 9: Spearman Rho Correlational Testing between Levels of Conversation of Rights' Practices in terms of Sustainable Development Goals among Children

Variables	Rho	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Conversation – Zero Hunger	0.2029	0.0201	Weak Positive	Significant
Conversation – Good Health and Well-being	0.4101	< .001	Moderate Positive	Significant
Conversation – Quality Education	0.4651	< .001	Moderate Positive	Significant

Table 9 presents the Spearman rho correlational testing results to determine the significant relationship between the level of conversation of the respondents and their rights' practice in terms of the SGD goals. As presented, all of the SGD goals such as zero hunger, good health and well-being, and quality education have significant relationships with the level of conversation. Given that all of their p-values are less than 0.05, the accepted margin of error of the study ($p = 0.0201, < 0.001$). Furthermore, all of them have positive relationships as well which means having direct relationships wherein both of the variables move in the same direction.

Specifically, the level of conversation has a weak positive relationship with zero hunger, which signifies that as the level of conversation increases, the level of child rights practice in terms of zero hunger increases also in a weak manner. The level of conversation has a moderate positive relationship with good health and well-being, which signifies that as the level of conversation increases, the level of child rights practice in terms of good health and well-being increases also in a moderate manner. Lastly, the level of conversation has a moderate positive relationship with quality education, which signifies that as the level of conversation increases, the level of child rights practice in terms of quality education increases also in a moderate manner.

Figure 5: Scatter Plot of Correlation between Level of Conversation and Rights' Practice in terms of Sustainable Development Goals among Children.

Figure 5 serves as the visual representation of the relationship between the levels of conversation and the rights practice in terms of the SGD goals of the respondents. As shown, as the level of conversation increases, the level of rights practice in terms of Sustainable Development Goals increases as well.

Table 10: Spearman Rho Correlational Testing between Levels of Conformity of Child Rights' Practices in terms of Sustainable Development Goals among Children.

Variables	Rho	p- value	Interpretation	Decision
Conformity – Zero Hunger	0.1581	0.0713	Very Weak Positive	Not Significant
Conformity – Good Health and Well-being	0.1969	0.0242	Very Weak Positive	Significant
Conformity – Quality Education	0.2756	0.0014	Weak Positive	Significant

Table 10 shows the Spearman rho correlational testing results to determine the significant relationship between the level of conformity of the respondents and their rights practice in terms of the Sustainable Development Goals. As presented, the goals such as good health and well-being and quality education have significant relationships with the level of conformity. Given that all of their p-values are less than 0.05, the accepted margin of error of the study ($p = 0.0242, 0.0014$). Moreover, these two have positive relationships as well, which means having direct relationships wherein both of the variables move in the same direction.

Specifically, the level of conformity has a moderate positive relationship with good health and well-being, which signifies that as the level of conversation increases, the level of child rights practice in terms of good health and well-being increases also in a very weak manner. Lastly, the level of conformity has a moderate positive

relationship with quality education, which signifies that as the level of conformity increases, the level of child rights practice in terms of quality education increases also in a weak manner.

Figure 6: Scatter Plot of Correlation between Level of Conformity and Rights' Practice in terms of Sustainable Development Goals among Children.

Figure 6 serves as the visual representation of the relationship between the levels of conformity and the rights practice in terms of SDG goals of the respondents. As shown, as the level of conformity increases, the level of child rights practice in terms of SDG goals increases as well.

In furthering the assessment of child rights practice, specifically in terms of Sustainable Development Goals such as zero hunger, good health and well-being and quality education, it was revealed as well that both high levels of conversation and conformity correlates to higher level of practice for imposing the requirements under zero hunger, good health and well-being and quality education ($r = 0.2029, 0.0713, 0.4101, 0.4651, 0.1581, 0.1969, 0.2756, p = 0.0201, 0.0242, < 0.001$). However, the

relationship between the high level of conformity and high level of practice for zero hunger is not significant, it cannot be denied the positive correlation that the two variables positions. With that, it is assured individually that all of the SGD goals that the proponent chose to highlight in the study are well experienced by the respondents.

Exploring these findings through the lenses of studies developed earlier, for Eden and Schrod (2019), highlighted that the practice of child rights are indeed crucial in the formation of founding policies that can help in sustaining both the needs and demands of child protection. And with the presence of family communication patterns, there is an effective understanding on improving the measures that familial environments should have to empower the child rights. On the other hand, Lansdown (2019) argued that in assuring that child rights practice are achieved through the widen experience of conversation and conformity elements, allow children to have a voice in the society. In this way, they are encouraged to express their views and participate in family discussions that can help in furthering their rights and awareness of the need for this.

Child Rights Practice for Each Family Communication Type

Consensual

Table 11: Spearman Rho Correlational Testing between Family Communication Patterns of Consensual Type in terms of Level of Conversation and Practice of Children's Rights

Variables	Rho	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Conversation of Consensual - Practice	0.22	0.0308	Weak Positive	Significant

Table 11 presents the Spearman rho correlational testing results in order to determine the significant relationship between the level of conversation of the respondents under the Consensual type of family communication pattern and their rights' practice. As shown, there is a weak positive relationship between the said variables ($r = 0.22$). This signifies that as the level of conversation of the respondents under the consensual type increases, their level of child rights' practice is also increasing and in a weak manner. This result is statistically significant at 95% confidence level ($p = 0.0308$).

Figure 7: Scatter Plot of Correlation between Family Communication Patterns of Consensual in terms of Level of Conversation and Rights' Practice among Children

Figure 7 serves as the visual representation of the relationship between the levels of conversation under the consensual family communication pattern and the rights practice of the respondents. As shown, as the level of conversation increases, the level of rights' practice also increases, and in a weak manner.

Table 12: Spearman Rho Correlational Testing between Family Communication Patterns of Consensual in terms of Level of Conformity and Rights' Practice among Children.

Variables	Rhop-value	Interpretation	Decision
Conformity of Consensual - Practice	0.02	0.0032	Very Weak Positive Significant

Table 12 shows the Spearman rho correlational testing results in order to determine the significant relationship between level of conformity of the respondents under consensual type of family communication pattern and their rights' practice. As presented, there is a very weak positive relationship between the said variables ($r = 0.02$). This signifies that as the level of conformity of the respondents under the

consensual type increases, their level of rights' practice is also increasing and in a very weak manner. This result is statistically significant at 95% confidence level ($p = 0.0032$).

Figure 8: Scatter Plot of Correlation between Family Communication Patterns of Consensual in terms of Level of Conformity and Rights' Practice among Children

Figure 8 illustrates the relationship between the levels of conformity under the consensual family communication pattern and the rights' practice of the respondents. As presented, as the level of conformity increases, the level of rights' practice also increases, and in a very weak manner.

Making the findings more specific with the relationship of family communication patterns and child rights practice, each type of family communication is studied for the determination of their implication to the practice. In consensual families, the weak positive correlation between conversation and rights practice ($r = 0.22$, $p = 0.0308$) indicates that even within a framework of high conformity, open communication is pivotal. This supports the notion that fostering an environment where children feel

heard enhances their understanding and practice of their rights. Hessel and Dworkin (2018) emphasize that in such environments, children learn to balance respect for family norms with their own rights and responsibilities. Consensual families, by promoting both dialogue and adherence to norms, create an environment where children can thrive both socially and emotionally.

Pluralistic

Table 13. Spearman Rho Correlational Testing between Family Communication Patterns of Pluralistic in terms of Level of Conversation and Rights' Practice among Children.

Variables	Rho	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Conversation of Pluralistic - Practice	0.49	0.0314	Moderate Positive	Significant

Table 13 positions the Spearman rho correlational testing results in order to determine the significant relationship between level of conversation of the respondents under pluralistic type of family communication pattern and their rights' practice. As shown, there is a moderate positive relationship between the said variables ($r = 0.49$). This signifies that as the level of conversation of the respondents under the pluralistic type increases, their level of rights' practice is also increasing and in a moderate manner. This result is statistically significant at 95% confidence level ($p = 0.0314$)

Figure 9. Scatter Plot of Correlation between Family Communication Patterns of Pluralistic in terms of Level of Conversation and Rights Practice among Children

Figure 9 serves as the visual representation of the relationship between the levels of conversation under the pluralistic family communication pattern and the rights' practice of the respondents. As shown, as the level of conversation increases, the level of rights' practice also increases, and in a moderate manner.

Table 14. Spearman Rho Correlational Testing between Family Communication Patterns of Pluralistic in terms of Level of Conformity and Rights' Practice among Children.

Variables	Rhop-value	Interpretation	Decision
Conformity of Pluralistic - Practice	0.02	0.0095	Very Weak Positive Significant

Table 14 positions the Spearman rho correlational testing results in order to determine the significant relationship between level of conformity of the respondents under pluralistic type of family communication pattern and their rights' practice. As presented, there is a very weak positive relationship between the said variables ($r = 0.02$). This signifies that as the level of conformity of the respondents under the

pluralistic type increases, their level of rights' practice is also increasing and in a very weak manner. This result is statistically significant at 95% confidence level ($p = 0.0314$).

Figure 10. Scatter Plot of Correlation between Family Communication Patterns of Pluralistic in terms of Level of Conformity and Children's Rights Practice

Figure 10 serves as the visual representation of the relationship between the levels of conformity under the pluralistic family communication pattern and the rights' practice of the respondents. As presented, as the level of conformity increases, the level of rights' practice also increases, and in a very weak manner. In pluralistic families, the moderate positive correlation between conversation and rights practice ($r = 0.49$, $p = 0.0314$) underscores the significant impact of open dialogue in environments with low conformity. This suggests that in less structured family settings, effective communication is even more critical for promoting children's rights. Koerner and Schrodtt (2018) argue that in such families, children are encouraged to express their views freely, which supports their understanding and practice of their rights. Pluralistic families, by fostering open dialogue and allowing for greater individual autonomy, provide an environment where children can develop a strong sense of self and agency.

Protective

Table 15: Spearman Rho Correlational Testing between Family Communication Patterns of Protective in terms of Level of Conversation And Children’s Rights Practice

Variables	Rho	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Conversation of Protective - Practice	-0.23	0.1326	Weak Negative	Not Significant

Table 15 demonstrates the spearman rho correlational testing results in order to determine the significant relationship between level of conversation of the respondents under protective type of family communication pattern and their rights’ practice. As shown, there is a weak negative relationship between the said variables ($r = -0.23$). This signifies that as the level of conversation of the respondents under the protective type increases, their level of rights’ practice decreases on the other hand in a weak manner, and vice versa. Though this result is not statistically significant at 95% confidence level ($p = 0.1326$).

Figure 11. Scatter Plot of Correlation between Family Communication Patterns of Protective in terms of Level of Conversation and Children’s Rights Practice.

Figure 11 serves as the visual representation of the relationship between the levels of conversation under the protective family communication pattern and the rights' practice of the respondents. As shown, as the level of conversation increases, the level of rights' practice decreases, and in a weak manner. However again, this is not statistically significant.

Table 16: Spearman Rho Correlational Testing between Family Communication Patterns of Protective in terms of Level of Conformity and Children's Rights Practice

Variables	Rho	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Conformity of Protective - Practice	-0.11	0.2977	Very Weak Negative	Not Significant

Table 16 presents the Spearman rho correlational testing results to determine the significant relationship between level of conformity of the respondents under protective type of family communication pattern and their rights' practice. As presented, there is a very weak negative relationship between the said variables ($r = -0.11$). This signifies that as the level of conformity of the respondents under the protective type increases, their level of rights' practice decreases on the other hand in a very weak manner, and vice versa. This result is not statistically significant at 95% confidence level ($p = 0.2977$).

Figure 12. Scatter Plot of Correlation between Family Communication Patterns of Protective in terms of Level of Conformity and Children's Rights Practice

Figure 12 serves as the visual representation of the relationship between the levels of conformity under the protective family communication pattern and the rights' practice of the respondents. As presented, as the level of conformity increases, the level of rights' practice decreases, and in a very weak manner. Though again, this is not statistically significant.

Conversely, in protective families, a weak negative correlation between conversation and rights practice ($r = -0.23$, $p = 0.1326$) suggests that high conformity without adequate conversation may impede children's rights practice, highlighting the need for balanced communication. Buehler, Franck, and Cook (2020) discuss that overly rigid family structures with limited dialogue can restrict children's ability to practice their rights effectively. In such settings, children may feel constrained and unable to voice their concerns or opinions, which can hinder their ability to understand and advocate for their rights.

Laissez-Faire

Table 17: Spearman Rho Correlational Testing between Family Communication Patterns of Laissez-Faire in terms of Level of Conversation and Children’s Rights Practice

Variables	Rho	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Conversation of Laissez-faire - Practice	-0.23	0.1944	Weak Negative	Not Significant

Table 17 shows the spearman rho correlational testing results in order to determine the significant relationship between level of conversation of the respondents under laissez-faire type of family communication pattern and their rights’ practice. As shown, there is a weak negative relationship between the said variables ($r = -0.23$).

This signifies that as the level of conversation of the respondents under the laissez-faire type increases, their level of rights’ practice decreases on the other hand in a weak manner, and vice versa. Though this result is not statistically significant at 95% confidence level ($p = 0.2977$).

Figure 13: Scatter Plot of Correlation between Family Communication Patterns of Laissez-Faire in terms of Level of Conversation and Child Rights’ Practice among Children.

Figure 13 serves as the visual representation of the relationship between the levels of conversation under the laissez-faire family communication pattern and the rights' practice of the respondents. As shown, as the level of conversation increases, the level of rights' practice decreases, and in a weak manner. Though again, this is not statistically significant.

Table 18: Spearman Rho Correlational Testing between Family Communication Patterns of Laissez-Faire in terms of Level of Conformity and Child's Rights Practice

Variables	Rho	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Conformity of Laissez-faire - Practice	-0.11	0.3419	Very Weak Negative	Not Significant

Table 18 positions the spearman rho correlational testing results in order to determine the significant relationship between level of conformity of the respondents under laissez-faire type of family communication pattern and their rights' practice. As presented, there is a very weak negative relationship between the said variables ($r = -0.11$). This signifies that as the level of conformity of the respondents under the laissez-faire type increases, their level of rights' practice decreases on the other hand in a very weak manner, and vice versa. Though this result is not statistically significant at 95% confidence level ($p = 0.2977$).

Figure 14: Scatter Plot of Correlation between Family Communication Patterns of Laissez-Faire in terms of Level of Conformity and Rights Practice among Children.

Figure 14 serves as the visual representation of the relationship between the levels of conformity under the laissez-faire family communication pattern and the rights' practice of the respondents. As presented, as the level of conformity increases, the level of rights' practice decreases, and in a very weak manner. Though again, this is not statistically significant.

Laissez-faire families, characterized by low levels of both conversation and conformity, show a weak negative relationship between conversation and rights practice ($r = -0.23$, $p = 0.1944$), indicating that the absence of structured communication and norms may undermine children's understanding and practice of their rights. Eden and Schrod (2019) highlight that in such environments, the lack of guidance and support can hinder children's ability to navigate their rights effectively. In laissez-faire families, the lack of both structured norms and open communication can lead to an environment where children feel neglected and unsupported, making it difficult for them to understand and advocate for their rights.

Table 19: Frequency and Percentage of Respondents in Terms of Type of Family Communication Pattern and Practice of Child's Rights

No. of Respondents	Types of Family Communication Patterns	Practice of Child Rights	Percent
75	Consensual	High	4.30
25	Protective	High	3.78
16	Laissez-Faire	High	3.63
15	Pluralistic	High	4.07

Table 19 shows the total tally of the respondents, the revealed type of Family Communication being practiced with their respective families and how the rights of the respondents are being practiced to each pattern. It depicts the level of how the basic rights of children specifically Sustainable Development Goals 2 Zero Hunger, 3 Good Health and Well-Being and 4 Quality Education are being achieved.

These findings collectively underscore the importance of fostering open and supportive communication within families to promote the practice of children's rights. They suggest that while conformity to family norms is important, it should not come at the expense of open dialogue between family members. Instead, a balanced approach that emphasizes both open communication and respect for family norms is essential

for fostering a conducive environment for children's rights practice. UNICEF (2019) highlights that children's rights to be heard and to express their views are fundamental principles that should be upheld within all family structures. Promoting a balanced approach where both dialogue and conformity are valued can help create an environment where children feel safe, respected, and empowered to practice their rights effectively. This balanced approach not only supports children's development and well-being but also prepares them to be active and responsible members of society.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

This study aimed to find the relationship of Family Communication Patterns to Child Rights Practice. It has identified the existing Family Communication Pattern of each research respondent and has examined its relationship with the realization of children's rights. Specifically, this research aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the different family communication patterns that exist within Filipino families?
2. What is the relationship between family communication patterns and child rights practice among children?

The study was conducted at the entire population of Silang West Elementary School Intermediate (Grade Six) Students in Silang Cavite. A total of 131 students have answered the survey questionnaires while 25 students were absent on the day the survey questionnaires were completed and one student did not fill out the survey.

The study has utilized a descriptive type of survey divided into two parts. The first one was adopted from Richie and Fitzpatrick's (2002) *Family Communication Patterns Questionnaire* where subcategories were included to measure the level of Conversation and Conformity, thus, identifying the type of Family Communication Pattern that existed. The second part of the survey was personally devised by the

researcher to expose how children's rights are practiced within the family which will be based on World Health Organizations' Sustainable Development Goals: Zero Hunger, Good Health and Well-Being and Quality Education.

Summary of Findings

With the main findings of the study, it was revealed that respondents fall under various family communication patterns. The sample of the study was able to gather representatives from consensual, pluralistic, protective, and laissez-faire types wherein the majority are from consensual while the least are from pluralistic. It was also determined that there is a significant relationship between family communication patterns and child rights practice, specifically under consensual and pluralistic types. With that, the researcher was able to prove the first and second hypotheses wherein consensual and pluralistic types of family communication patterns lead to a high level of child rights practice. The other two-family communication patterns such as protective and laissez-faire do not lead to a high level of child rights practice, as they yielded insignificant results. Specifically, the following is the summary of findings:

1. In the determination of family communication patterns, the majority of the sample is under the consensual type with a total of 75 respondents. This is followed by the protective type of communication pattern with 25 respondents. Then the laissez-faire type with 16 respondents. Lastly, the pluralistic type of communication pattern with only 15 respondents.

2. Taking into consideration both the presence of levels of conversation and conformity in determining the groupings of family communication patterns, both of them combined, lead to high levels of child rights practice in all types such as consensual, pluralistic, and laissez-faire. The group with the highest child rights practice is consensual with a median of 4.30, followed by pluralistic with 4.07, then protective with 3.78, and lastly laissez-faire with 3.63.
3. Separating the two factors in the determination of family communication patterns, the first one, which is the conversation orientation, has a statistically significant moderate positive relationship with child rights practice.
4. On the other hand, another vital factor in the determination of family communication patterns is conformity orientation, which has a statistically significant weak positive relationship with child rights practice.
5. Lastly, in terms of the establishment of the correlation between family communication patterns and child rights practice. Individually assessing the consensual, pluralistic, protective, and laissez-faire patterns, with the child rights practice, only the consensual and pluralistic types have significant relationships with child rights practice. This sustains the earlier findings that as the level of conversation and conformity increases, the level of child rights practice also increases. On the other hand, those respondents under the protective and laissez-faire types do not sustain enough evidence to claim significant relationships with child rights practice.

Conclusions

A family being a basic institution plays a vital role in the rearing and development of a child. Each individual is raised by an elder who molds and secures the child's value and dignity as a person and as a member of society. Being the basic unit where a child grows, the family is expected to protect and strengthen the life of a child and this includes the realization and practice of child rights.

This study has revealed that the different ways in which we interact and communicate with our family members have a direct impact on how child rights are practiced. In determining of presence of various family communication patterns among the target population, the respondents of this study were able to confirm the different types of Family Communication Patterns as existing and how each of these patterns impacts the practice of child rights.

Incorporating the employed sets of hypotheses in the study in order to analyze if there is a significant relationship between family communication pattern and child rights practice indeed a consensual type of family communication leads to high level of practice of child rights. This goes synonymous to the pluralistic type of family communication, which also leads to high level of practice of child rights. For protective type of family communication, only under the factor of high level of conformity that leads to high level of practice of child rights. And under the laissez-faire type of family communication, the presented results under levels of conversation and conformity are not enough yet to statistically claim that this pattern communication leads to a high level of practice of child's rights.

Overall, the study was able to determine that individual types of family communication specifically, consensual, pluralistic and protective have significant positive relationships with the practice of child rights. And, generally, both the levels of conversation and conformity have significant positive relationships with the practice of child rights. With that, this study serves as the foundation of imposition that in order to strengthen the practice of child rights among Filipino families, there is a need to improve the conversation and conformity elements of family communications. This proves that familial connection indeed is a viable factor in empowering the determination and enactment of child rights here in the Philippines.

The specific rights that the proponent highlighted in the study, all of them were proven to be achieved through the empowerment of family communication patterns. Zero hunger, good health and well-being, and quality education were only the primary aspects that constitute the main needs of the children. And if they were practiced through the strengthening of family communication, this can also be done with the other aspects of the needs of the children today. Especially that he needs and demands for the general well-being of children are continuously progressing, the factors that affect this, should be further assessed and studied. This study may serve as one of the continuous academic discussions on how society and institutions must act upon the progress of lives of the children through developmental communication.

Implications of the Study

The study revealed that all four family communication patterns such as consensual, pluralistic, protective, and laissez-faire were evident in the sample. Out of these four, consensual was the most prevalent pattern exercised among the participants' familial communication.

In terms of assessing the relationship between family communication patterns and practice of child rights, the factors of conversation and conformity were measured. The general findings without the groupings of the patterns yet showed that as both levels of conversation and conformity are increasing, the practice of child rights is increasing as well. This implies that without taking into consideration the patterns yet; to improve the practice of child rights, the conversation and conformity aspects of familial relationships need to be empowered.

Observing individually the family communication patterns, there were also significant relationships with their respective levels of conversation and conformity with the practice of child rights. The participants with consensual patterns, it was revealed that as their levels of conversation and conformity are increasing, the practice of child rights was increasing as well. This goes the same with the respondents under the pluralistic communication pattern. However, in the protective type of family communication, the relationships of the variables were inverse. This presented that as the levels of conversation and conformity are increasing, the practice of child rights is decreasing on the other hand, and vice versa. This was also the result for the participants under laissez-faire. Given these inverse or negative relationships, they

are bound to produce insignificant results. Overall, only the consensual and pluralistic patterns stimulated statistically significant positive relationships.

With the specific findings in the individual patterns and the dependent variable, which is the practice of child rights, the general outcomes before groupings of the family communication patterns are substantial in determining the results. As shown, the practice of child rights can be improved through increasing levels of conversation and conformity which was reflected in the individual relationships of the patterns with the practice of child rights. Among the four patterns, only the consensual and pluralistic were able to produce similar findings which is a positive relationship - these two patterns claimed to be significant. With these findings, it can be implied that any result not following the general findings is indeed bound to be insignificant. Hence, the decisions on the tests conducted under protective and laissez-faire were insignificant.

Overall, the inferred implication of the findings states that the sample's ideal family communication pattern for promoting high practice of child rights is consensual. This was reflected both in the general and individual relationship testing. One notable aspect to highlight is pluralism. Although pluralism has a high level of conversation but a low level of conformity, pluralistic respondents have revealed that they aim to achieve the consensual pattern where their practice of child rights increases when their level of conformity increases. This supports the argument that respondents favoring consensual communication, which emphasizes high levels of both conversation and conformity, are better positioned to enhance the practice of child rights. The findings suggest that the consensual communication pattern, characterized by high levels of both conversation and conformity, is the most effective for promoting

the practice of child rights among families. The significant positive relationship observed within both the general and individual analyses supports the notion that fostering these elements within family dynamics can lead to better outcomes in the practice of child rights.

Recommendations

Integrating all the findings and conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations are suggested:

A. For Further Research

1. Types of Family Based on Authority - Since the study is focused on examining the relationship of the existing Family Communication Patterns with Child Rights Practice, it is suggested that further study be conducted on the effects of Familial Authority (*Patriarchal, Matriarchal, Nuclear, extended and Joint*) on Family Communication Patterns and Child Rights Practice. Such research can further investigate if there is a direct impact on the existing authority with the way the family communicates and practices children's rights.

2. Digital Communication and Family Communication Pattern – As the research was conducted, it was revealed that some of the respondents have Overseas Filipino Workers as parents. As the digital world continues to advance, identifying the increasing use of digital tools as a means of communication can help assess its effects on the existing family communication patterns and child rights practice. It can also investigate the benefits and challenges of digital communication in maintaining the positive dynamics of family communication.

3. Child Rights and Culture – For further studies dealing with children's rights, it is also an interesting focus to consider the culture where the child grew up. Cultural

practices can influence how a child is disciplined and understanding this factor can shape the perception and affect how their rights are realized and practiced. This study can also aid in developing culturally sensitive and effective child rights policies and interventions.

4. Comparison of the Relationship of Family Communication Patterns and Children's Practice of Rights between Male and Female - This can be a continuous study for future researchers who plan to further the research regarding the relationship between family communication patterns and practice of child rights, in terms of comparing the results between males and females. It can be observed that between these two, they exhibit different emotional and communicative behaviors. Since this can be influenced by family dynamics, it is important to explore as well on how this can be incorporated about the study.

B. For the Respondents / Educational Institution

1. Child Rights Education in School Curriculum - Knowledge of students on their rights and privileges as individuals will raise awareness of their rights and responsibilities. According to the School Guidance Counselor of the Research subject, it is indeed included in the curriculum of the primary students (Grade 2) and is integrated into the modules yearly. Having Child Rights Education as a subject itself where age-appropriate learning materials and activities can be developed encourages respect for diversity, inclusion, and empathy towards one self and others. This can create a strong foundation that can empower students as valued members of society.

2. Engage with Stakeholders– Conspire and participate with parents and students with the goal of realizing and enhancing the SDG related initiatives. A strong partnership between the school, parents and students will enable to address food scarcity, health conditions and literacy issues. Aside from the snacks “feeding” made available to students, a regular meal plan that is nutritious and budget conscious can be suggested everyday to facilitate better nutrition for children. A close coordination with the local health centers can also be conducted to monitor the health and records of each and every student. The learning capacity of the child can be further enhanced by making sure that every parent / guardian allows quality time at home to review and go over the school lessons and needs.

3. Counselling and Support Services. A delegated Guidance Counsellor is accessible for all schools, always on hand to help the students with any conflict that each may encounter. However, a strong support on addressing family dynamics and promoting healthy relationships can attend to students and families experiencing communication challenges or conflicts. Ensuring access to school-based counseling and support can provide a comprehensive support system that addresses the whole well-being of students enhancing their ability to succeed in school and beyond.

C. For the Local Government / Municipality / LGU

1. Community / Barangay Workshop on Family Communication and Child Rights – Facilitate educational workshops for parents or guardians that would educate the community on not only knowing the children's rights but also the value of respecting and putting the rights into practice. These programs can also promote

effective family communication and how children can be involved in decision-making that empowers them as individuals and as valued member of the society. Aside from parents /guardians, community members, local leaders can also engage in these workshops to learn practical strategies on fostering positive family relationships.

2. Establish and Implement Comprehensive Policies – Implementing policies that will ensure that each child in the community has access to nutritious food through community kitchens, free health check-ups and immunizations including emergency cases and zero payment/contribution to all school children most especially those in the lower income households. Sufficient investment on furthering the training and knowledge of teachers while being equipped with the necessary tools.

3. Child Friendly Policies. Community leaders should consider children as vital members of society just like adults. In the province of Cavite, only the municipality of Silang has a delegated office for the Women’s and Children’s Protection Unit. Offices like *WCPU* in Silang should be made available in other municipalities as it focuses and attends to various concerns of women and children. Community leaders and policymakers should also establish support initiatives like affordable child care and family friendly workplaces.

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Appendix A

Mr. John Christian Paolo M. Belen

Psychometrician
DSWD – WCPU
Silang, Cavite

Dear Sir Belen,

I hope this letter finds you well. I am **Mary Rocelle A. Binaoro**, a graduate student under the Masters of Development Communication program at the University of the Philippines Open University. I am currently pursuing my graduate thesis entitled:

Family Communication Patterns and Practice of Child Rights Among Intermediate Elementary Students in a School in Silang, Cavite

I am writing to you seeking your invaluable expertise as a psychometrician in reviewing my thesis questionnaire on child rights practice. The focus of my research is to explore the existing family communication patterns among intermediate students and understand their relationship to child rights practice and it is of utmost importance that the questionnaire used in the study is not only valid and reliable but also age-appropriate and child-friendly. I am reaching out to request your support in ensuring the quality and appropriateness of the questions included in the questionnaire.

I have attached a copy of the questionnaire for your perusal. I kindly ask that you review the questions and provide feedback on their appropriateness for the target age group, ensuring that they adhere to ethical standards and are framed in a manner conducive to obtaining accurate and reliable responses from the children.

Thank you very much for your time and consideration.

Mary Rocelle A. Binaoro
Student #: 1998-04146

Appendix B

CERTIFICATE OF CONSULTATION AND VALIDATION

This is to certify that the student researchers namely:

Mary Rocelle A. Binaoro

with the thesis title:

**FAMILY COMMUNICATION PATTERNS AND PRACTICE OF CHILD RIGHTS
AMONG INTERMEDIATE ELEMENTARY STUDENTS
IN A SCHOOL IN SILANG, CAVITE**

respectfully communicated and requested consultation and **validation for their quantitative data collection and analyses** that they will use as part of their requirements in their thesis.

I have reviewed, advised necessary changes, and validated the proposed data collection and analyses. The contents of the methodology presented by the students are accurate to meet the goals of their thesis investigation.

Certification issued by:

Umpara, Samraine M.

Name and signature of the Statistician

Affiliation: University of the Philippines - Diliman

E-mail: smumpara@up.edu.ph

July 30, 2024

Date Issued

Appendix C

Mdme. Gina Lejos

Silang West Elementary School

Silang, Cavite

Dear Mdme. Lejos:

Good day! I am Mary Rocelle A. Binaoro, a second-year graduate student in Masters of Development Communication at the University of the Philippines – Open University. I am currently pursuing my graduate thesis entitled:

**Family Communication Patterns and Practice of Child Rights
Among Intermediate Elementary Students in a School in Silang, Cavite**

I would like to ask your permission to gather data from your Elementary Intermediate Grade Six students through a survey questionnaire. The research instrument will determine the existing type of Communication Patterns in the students' Families and how this identified context affects the communication and practice of children's rights within the family.

Rest assured that the information gathered will be dealt with utmost confidentiality and will only be used for the sole purpose of this research. Your assistance will be of great help in the accomplishment of this study.

Hoping for your kind consideration.

Respectfully Yours:

Mary Rocelle A. Binaoro

Student #: 98-04146

Noted By:

Dr. Alexander Flor

Thesis Advis

Appendix D

Good Day!

I am Mary Rocelle A. Binaoro, a Graduate student of Masters of Development Communication at the University of the Philippines – Open University and currently pursuing my master thesis entitled:

Family Communication Patterns and Practice of Child Rights Among Intermediate Elementary Students in a School in Silang, Cavite

In this regard, I would like to ask your permission (by signing below) to allow your son/daughter to fill out a survey questionnaire that would assess the following objectives:

1. Identify the different family communication patterns
2. Describe the communication process in communicating child's rights based on family communication pattern
3. Explain and determine the relationship between family communication patterns and child rights practice among children.

Rest assured that all responses will be dealt with utmost confidentiality and will only be used for the sole purpose of this study.

Respectfully Yours:

Ms. Mary Rocelle A. Binaoro

mabinaoro@up.edu.ph

Parent's / Guardian's Name and Signature

Son / Daughter's Name:

Appendix E

Good day!

I am Mary Rocelle A. Binaoro, a second year graduate student in Master of Development Communication at the University of the Philippines – Open University. I am currently pursuing my graduate thesis entitled:

Family Communication Patterns and Practice of Child Rights Among Intermediate Elementary Students in a School in Silang, Cavite

This study aims to understand how certain family communication patterns affect the realization of children's rights within Filipino families. In this regard, may I request for you to fill out the survey below to gather all the needed data necessary in the accomplishment of this research. Kindly check or encircle your answer accordingly without leaving any item unanswered.

Rest assured that all information will be dealt with confidentiality and will only be used for the purpose of this study.

Thank you very much.

REVISED FAMILY COMMUNICATION PATTERNS QUESTIONNAIRE

Name: (Optional): _____

Age: _____

Section: _____

Sex: _____

Instructions: The following questionnaire was adopted from Koerner and Fitzpatrick in 2002. Carefully read each situation stated below. Kindly check whichever applies to you.

- 1 – Strongly Disagree
- 2 – Disagree
- 3 – Neutral
- 4 – Agree
- 5 – Strongly Agree

Reference: Koerner, A. F., & Fitzpatrick, M. A. (2002). The Revised Family Communication Pattern Instrument (Parent & Child versions) including scoring instructions. *ResearchGate*.

<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15136.64000>

1 – Strongly Disagree 2 – Disagree 3 – Neutral 4 – Agree 5 – Strongly Agree

PART 1 - A. Conversation Orientation

	1	2	3	4	5
1. In our family, we often talk about topics like politics and religion where some persons disagree with others.					
2. My parents often say something like “Every member of the family should have some say in family decisions.”					
3. My parents often ask my opinion when the family is talking about something.					
4. My parents encourage me to challenge their ideas and beliefs.					
5. My parents often say something like “You should always look at both sides of an issue.”					
6. I usually tell my parents what I am thinking about things.					
7. I can tell my parents almost anything.					
8. In our family, we often talk about our feelings and emotions.					
9. My parents and I often have long, relaxed conversations about nothing in particular.					
10. I really enjoy talking with my parents, even when we disagree.					
11. My parents encourage me to express my feelings.					
12. My parents tend to be very often about their emotions.					
13. We often talk as a family about things we have done during the day.					
14. In our family, we often talk about our plans and hopes for the future.					
15. My parents like to hear my opinion, even when I don’t agree with them.					

1 – Strongly Disagree 2 – Disagree 3 – Neutral 4 – Agree 5 – Strongly Agree

B. Conformity Orientation

	1	2	3	4	5
1. When anything really important is involved, my parents expect me to obey without question.					
2. In our home, my parents usually have the last word.					
3. My parents feel that it is important to be the boss.					
4. My parents sometimes become irritated with my views if they are different from theirs.					
5. If my parents don't approve of it, they don't want to know about it.					
6. When I am at home, I am expected to obey my parents' rules.					
7. My parents often say things like "You'll know better when you grow up."					
8. My parents often say things like "My ideas are right and you should not question them."					
9. My parents often say things like "A child should not argue with adults."					
10. My parents often say things like "There are some things that just shouldn't be talked about."					
11. My parents often say things like "You should give in on arguments rather than risk making people mad."					

1 – Strongly Disagree 2 – Disagree 3 – Neutral 4 – Agree 5 – Strongly Agree

Part 2 –Practice of Children’s Rights within the Family

	1	2	3	4	5
1. In my family, my parents/guardians make sure I eat nutritious food three times a day.					
2. My parents/guardians encourages me to eat nutritious food like meat, fish, bread, milk, fruits and vegetables.					
3. In my family, we have a clean source of drinking water.					
4. My parents/guardians provide me with enough school snack and drinks whenever I attend my classes or go out of the house.					
5. My parents support my growth by giving me oral vitamins and supplements.					
6. My parents / guardians take care of me when I am sick.					
7. My parents/guardians bring me to health center / hospital whenever needed.					
8. My parents/guardians make sure that I have complete vaccines.					
9. As a growing individual, my parents educate me with the different physical changes that I will be going through and provides the necessary support needed.					
10. During times when public health is at stake like Covid 19, my parents make sure that I am protected and safe.					
11. My parents/guardians make sure that I get enrolled in school every year.					
12. My parents/guardians spend time with me in learning my lessons at school.					
13. My parents/guardians make sure I have everything I need for school.					
14. My parents/guardians allow me to join social activities and organizations in school like field trips, seminars and school clubs.					
15. Whenever needed, my parents adapts to the changing needs of the learning system such as the acquisition of tablets or cellphones to support online learning.					

<https://web.coa.gov.ph/sdg/index.php/goals/sdg/zero-hunger/>

<https://chr.gov.ph/statement-of-the-commission-on-human-rights-in-support-of-the-passage-of-the-magna-carta-of-children-bill/>

<https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/hunger/>

<https://web.coa.gov.ph/sdg/index.php/goals/sdg/good-health-and-well-being/>

<https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/health/>

<https://web.coa.gov.ph/sdg/index.php/goals/sdg/quality-education/>

<https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/education/>

Appendix F

Descriptive Statistics of Levels of Conversation, Conformity and Childs' Rights Practice of each Respondent.

Respondent Number	Level of Conversation	Conversation Interpretation	Level of Conformity	Conformity Interpretation	Level of Child's Rights Practice	Practice Interpretation
1	3.40	High	4.00	High	4.00	High
2	3.07	High	3.73	High	4.07	High
3	2.80	Low	3.36	High	4.00	High
4	2.53	Low	2.91	Low	4.20	High
5	2.53	Low	3.00	Low	4.00	High
6	2.73	Low	3.18	High	3.93	High
7	4.27	High	2.64	Low	3.73	High
8	2.93	Low	3.45	High	4.40	High
9	2.93	Low	3.55	High	4.67	High
10	4.07	High	2.55	Low	2.07	Low
11	2.93	Low	3.55	High	4.87	High
12	3.40	High	4.00	High	3.93	High
13	3.33	High	4.00	High	3.60	High
14	3.80	High	5.00	High	3.87	High
15	3.73	High	4.55	High	4.87	High
16	3.36	High	4.00	High	3.93	High
17	3.93	High	2.45	Low	4.00	High
18	3.73	High	4.45	High	4.53	High
19	2.87	Low	3.45	High	4.00	High
20	3.13	High	3.82	High	4.67	High
21	2.80	Low	3.27	High	3.33	High
22	2.20	Low	2.73	Low	2.87	Low
23	2.93	Low	3.45	High	4.13	High
24	3.27	High	3.91	High	4.53	High
25	3.20	High	3.91	High	4.00	High
26	2.87	Low	3.36	High	4.93	High
27	3.00	Low	3.64	High	4.13	High
28	2.87	Low	3.45	High	4.33	High
29	4.13	High	2.55	Low	2.73	Low
30	3.60	High	4.36	High	5.00	High
31	2.93	Low	3.45	High	3.40	High
32	3.40	High	4.00	High	4.67	High
33	3.20	High	3.82	High	4.00	High
34	2.67	Low	3.09	High	5.00	High
35	2.93	Low	3.55	High	4.80	High
36	3.40	High	4.18	High	4.33	High

37	2.07	Low	2.64	Low	4.93	High
38	3.67	High	4.36	High	4.80	High
39	1.80	Low	2.18	Low	4.87	High
40	2.20	Low	2.73	Low	3.00	Low
41	2.67	Low	3.18	High	5.00	High
42	3.13	High	3.82	High	4.07	High
43	3.47	High	4.27	High	3.93	High
44	3.07	High	3.73	High	5.00	High
45	3.40	High	4.00	High	3.00	Low
46	3.13	High	3.82	High	4.47	High
47	2.80	Low	3.36	High	4.60	High
48	3.07	High	3.73	High	3.93	High
49	2.00	Low	2.36	Low	5.00	High
50	3.57	High	4.36	High	4.20	High
51	2.60	Low	3.09	High	5.00	High
52	3.27	High	3.91	High	4.27	High
53	3.20	High	3.91	High	4.00	High
54	2.33	Low	2.73	Low	4.00	High
55	4.00	High	2.45	Low	3.80	High
56	3.93	High	2.27	Low	3.67	High
57	3.00	Low	3.64	High	4.07	High
58	3.20	High	3.91	High	4.00	High
59	3.53	High	4.27	High	4.60	High
60	2.73	Low	3.27	High	4.07	High
61	3.40	High	4.18	High	4.47	High
62	3.07	High	3.73	High	5.00	High
63	2.73	Low	3.18	High	4.27	High
64	2.07	Low	2.55	Low	3.80	High
65	1.27	Low	1.64	Low	3.27	High
66	2.60	Low	3.00	Low	4.33	High
67	3.40	High	4.00	High	4.80	High
68	3.93	High	2.27	Low	4.20	High
69	4.27	High	2.64	Low	3.73	High
70	4.80	High	2.73	Low	3.47	High
71	2.67	Low	3.09	High	4.07	High
72	3.80	High	4.73	High	3.80	High
73	2.43	Low	2.82	Low	5.00	High
74	2.80	Low	3.36	High	4.60	High
75	3.73	High	4.55	High	4.87	High
76	2.60	Low	3.09	High	4.00	High
77	2.80	Low	3.36	High	4.53	High
78	2.33	Low	2.73	Low	3.67	High
79	3.20	High	3.91	High	4.00	High
80	3.67	High	4.36	High	4.80	High
81	3.47	High	4.27	High	3.87	High

82	3.73	High	4.55	High	4.33	High
83	4.87	High	2.82	Low	4.20	High
84	3.07	High	3.73	High	4.50	High
85	3.80	High	4.82	High	5.00	High
86	3.87	High	5.00	High	4.27	High
87	3.80	High	4.82	High	4.40	High
88	3.73	High	4.55	High	4.27	High
89	3.73	High	4.64	High	4.87	High
90	3.60	High	4.36	High	3.87	High
91	4.07	High	2.55	Low	4.07	High
92	2.40	Low	2.82	Low	4.33	High
93	2.53	Low	3.00	Low	3.80	High
94	3.13	High	3.82	High	3.53	High
95	3.00	High	3.64	High	4.60	High
96	3.33	High	3.91	High	4.20	High
97	3.00	Low	3.64	High	4.27	High
98	3.20	High	3.91	High	4.00	High
99	3.00	Low	3.64	High	4.20	High
100	3.33	High	4.00	High	4.53	High
101	4.40	High	2.73	Low	2.87	Low
102	3.87	High	5.00	High	4.33	High
103	5.00	High	2.91	Low	3.33	High
104	5.00	High	3.27	High	4.60	High
105	5.00	High	3.27	High	3.33	High
106	5.00	High	3.18	High	3.80	High
107	5.00	High	3.55	High	4.13	High
108	5.00	High	3.64	High	3.67	High
109	5.00	High	3.18	High	4.20	High
110	5.00	High	3.09	High	3.87	High
111	5.00	High	4.09	High	3.93	High
112	5.00	High	3.91	High	4.73	High
113	5.00	High	3.91	High	4.00	High
114	5.00	High	4.09	High	4.27	High
115	5.00	High	3.64	High	4.07	High
116	5.00	High	3.27	High	3.07	High
117	5.00	High	3.36	High	4.27	High
118	5.00	High	3.45	High	3.47	High
119	5.00	High	4.73	High	2.73	Low
120	5.00	High	3.00	Low	4.60	High
121	5.00	High	3.09	High	3.27	High
122	5.00	High	3.09	High	3.33	High
123	5.00	High	3.55	High	2.07	Low
124	5.00	High	3.36	High	3.87	High
125	5.00	High	4.09	High	4.13	High
126	3.93	High	1.91	Low	3.93	High

127	5.00	High	4.73	High	3.33	High
128	5.00	High	4.09	High	4.00	High
129	5.00	High	2.91	Low	3.60	High
130	5.00	High	3.45	High	5.00	High
132	5.00	High	3.64	High	3.47	High

Appendix G

Descriptive Statistics on Level of Child's Right Practice In Different Family Communication Patterns in Terms of Sustainable Development Goal – Zero Hunger

Communication Type	Zero Hunger	Frequency	Percent
Consensual	High	68	90.6667
	Low	7	9.3333
	Total	75	100.0000
Laissez-Faire	High	14	87.5000
	Low	2	12.5000
	Total	16	100.0000
Pluralistic	High	14	93.3333
	Low	1	6.6667
	Total	15	100.0000
Protective	High	25	100.0000
	Low	0	0.0000
	Total	25	100.0000

Appendix H

Descriptive Statistics on Level of Child's Right Practice In Different Family Communication Patterns in terms of Sustainable Development Goal – Good Health and Well-Being

Communication Type Good Health and Well-being Frequency		
Consensual	High	70
	Low	5
	Total	75
Laissez-Faire	High	15
	Low	1
	Total	16
Pluralistic	High	14
	Low	1
	Total	15
Protective	High	23
	Low	2
	Total	25

Appendix I

Descriptive Statistics on Level of Child's Right Practice In Different Family
Communication Patterns in terms of Sustainable Development Goal –
Quality Education

Communication Type	Quality Education	Frequency	Percent
Consensual	High	70	93.3333
	Low	5	6.6667
	Total	75	100.0000
Laissez-Faire	High	14	87.5000
	Low	2	12.5000
	Total	16	100.0000
Pluralistic	High	11	73.3333
	Low	4	26.6667
	Total	15	100.0000
Protective	High	21	84.0000
	Low	4	16.0000
	Total	25	100.0000